

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated. I also declare that it has not been previously or concurrently submitted as a whole for any other degrees at any or other institutions.

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***This humble dissertation is dedicated to
Muslim&Non Muslims Brothers & Sisters
Those who work for the path of Almighty Allah Exalted
Those who seek the Truth***

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To two special persons whom I owe everything, my beloved wife and my mother who has encouraged and supported my study, this dissertation is dedicated to you.

Research Topic:

“Diplomacy And Islam/ Islamic Diplomacy/ International Social Relations in Islam”

Diplomacy is a reflection of the values of nations and peoples, their cultural and civilizational specificities, political choices, and their religious precepts and traditions. It is a portrait of the past, a reflection of the present and a vision of the future. Any form of diplomacy is built around the principles governing the political structure of the State it represents, whose interests it serves and whose entity it embodies abroad. Diplomacy can be defined as the art and science of conducting international relations. Diplomacy according to the Islamic Shari‘ah is one of the best ways to show the Islamic values, merits and advantages in conducting international affairs with non-Muslims. This research article explores the principles and tools of diplomacy used by Prophet in the first Islamic State of Madinah, and also to analyze the foundations and objectives of Islamic diplomacy. It further discusses briefly diplomacy under rightly guided Caliphs and also under banu Umayyad.

Introduction:

One of the oldest ways of solving disputes among human beings peacefully has been the diplomatic negotiation. Nowadays most of the nations use this method to ease strained relations, reduce hostility, and establish economical and political relations, as well as halting armed combats, and consolidating peace. Diplomatic interaction, being a universal bequest of antiquity was practiced in Islam right from the periods of Prophet Muhammad (SAW); the first four Caliphs; the Umayyad dynasty; the Abbasid Empire; down to the Ottoman Empire. Diplomacy is one of the most practical and dynamic topics of international relations; therefore, the religion of Islam since its beginning, has recognized this logical approach as one of the most important ways for conducting international affairs through ambassadors and envoys who use peaceful means. The Prophet (SAW) of Islam, with respect to existing traditions and Quranic teachings, signed diplomatic negotiations in ties with Arabian tribes and other states. The Prophet (SAW) implemented this method by delegating ambassadors or representatives to different countries. Prophet Muhammad's conducts were actually the reflection of all the Islamic principles like justice, tolerance, truthfulness and fair play to anyone.

IMPORTANCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY:

The importance of this study and its significance can be explained as follows: a. Diplomacy is the most important way of conducting international affairs; b. The practice of diplomacy according to the Islamic Shari'ah is one of the best ways to show the Islamic values, merits and advantages in conducting international affairs with non-Muslims; c. It is essential to explain diplomacy and its principles in Islam; d. It can guide some Muslim scholars who rely solely on the Western concept of diplomacy; e. It can be a warning to the Muslim Ummah (the Muslim Community) on the pitfalls of the Western theories, and at the same time it

could provide them with a comprehensive concept of diplomacy that Islam offers to mankind.

REASONS OF SELECTING THE TOPIC:

The reasons of selecting this topic can be traced back to the following points: a. Nobody has studied this subject as an independent topic; b. The diplomatic issues are very dynamic and are considered as the most important instrument for Muslim nations in conducting their external relations with others and facing the variable international affairs with suitable solutions; c. People are urgently required to understand diplomacy in Islam in a comprehensive way as an instrument embodying the concept of justice in Islam; d. My interest for researching this topic provides a good opportunity to read, benefit and learn, because this topic is inseparably related to the Holy Qur'ān, the Noble Sunnah, and Fiqh (Islamic Jurisprudence), etc.;

The Concept Of Diplomacy

The definition of diplomacy is usually presented on two levels. First, diplomacy is introduced as a general concept according to which everything a state does in the field of foreign policy is under the concept of diplomacy. For example, the definition of diplomacy "as the management of the entire foreign policy" (Holstie, 1995: 212). is one such definition. In this definition, even resorting to war is considered as part of a country's diplomacy, regardless of whether it is aimed at sending a message to the opposite actor or whether the purpose of resorting to war is to suppress and eliminate the actor. In contrast, diplomacy has a more specific application in the political sciences. In this particular application, diplomacy can be defined in terms of purpose or in terms of the manner in which it is applied. "In terms of purpose, the art of peacefully resolving international issues and disputes and countries' disputes peacefully" is called diplomacy. The definition of diplomacy considered in this article is the same diplomacy in a

specific sense, provided that it is not necessarily limited to formal negotiations, rather, it involves any process that involves sending a message and changing the mindset of other actors, even if the message is implicit.

Public Diplomacy

The term public diplomacy was first used in the United States in 1965 by Edmund Golwin, dean of the Faculty of Law and Diplomacy at Taft University, at the same time as the Edward Moore Center for Diplomacy opened. This center considers public diplomacy as a process of influencing public attitudes for the formation and implementation of foreign policy and includes dimensions of international relations that go beyond traditional diplomacy (Wolf and Rosen, 2005, p. 31.32: 94). The dictionary of International Relations, published by the State Department in 1985, defines public diplomacy as follows: "Public diplomacy refers to government-sponsored programs aimed at informing or influencing public opinion in other countries. Its main tools are the publication of text, moving images, cultural exchanges, and radio and television " (Kogli and Vatikov, 2003: 192). Public diplomacy should make it possible to improve and enhance relations between nations and governments. The assignment of such a task for public diplomacy is based on the premise that many misunderstandings between states and nations that make it impossible to establish peaceful and constructive communication between them stem from a lack of awareness and information. Increasing cultural exchanges increase the knowledge of nations and governments about each other, and this increase in knowledge eliminates the possibility of many misunderstandings, promotes the possibility of building constructive relations. In general, in expressing the differences between traditional and public diplomacy, it can be said that secrecy, unpopularity, bilateral relations, pragmatism and limited actors were among the characteristics of diplomacy in its traditional sense; however, characteristics such as openness, populism, multilateralism, broad participation and respect for nations are more than the characteristics of public diplomacy (Soltanifar, 2007: 45).

Islamic Conceptualization of Islamic Diplomacy

According to the principle of invitation, it can be said that public diplomacy in Islamic thought cannot be exactly equivalent to the concept that is common in the Western view. The goal of the invitation strategy is to reform all human beings, and every human being is in itself a goal whose guidance and reform is independently valuable. The goal of the invitation strategy is to reform all human beings, and every human being is in itself a goal whose guidance and reform is independently valuable, rather, it may be argued that in the original Islamic view, the relationship between the two is inverse and that the principle is the unity of human beings, and addressing governments is, in fact, a prelude to which conveying the call of invitation to divine and Islamic values to all individuals (Dehghani Firoozabadi, 2013, 3: 3). In public diplomacy, as is customary in the West, the "public" or "people" are valued because they are "citizens" of a state, and the more important and powerful that government is, the more important that "citizen" and those people become. But if the government has no power against it, its citizens can be ignored and enter into direct negotiations with the government and gain national interests. But in Islamic thought, people are valued because they are "human", not because they are citizens. Therefore, regardless of whether the government is powerful or not, its people are the target of this type of public diplomacy (Dehghani Firoozabadi, 2013, 3: 3). Western view of public diplomacy the "public" is seen merely as a means of exerting pressure on governments. The ultimate goal is the same as political goals and ambitions and the increase and expansion of domination. In the past, this goal was pursued through hard tools and covert diplomacy and deception and today, with the increasing share of public opinion in government policy-making, as well as the rise of communication technology and the Westerners' superiority in the use of this technology, less costly ways have been found to pursue those hegemonic goals that will likely lead to more lasting results. This diplomacy is not the result of a

belief in the "public" or the "people", so many see it as a "necessary evil" or a "side tactic" that should support "conventional diplomacy efforts". Even in some attitudes toward public diplomacy, the people of the target community are more likely to be viewed as prey that is supposed to turn them into regular customers of Western cultural products in order to glamor Western culture. Given that the purpose of Islam in public diplomacy is to reform and guide human beings, the Islamic definition of public diplomacy can be expressed as follows: Exchange of "facts" in twoway communication based on human "nature" with the aim of pursuing and securing "human interests" (Dehghani Firoozabadi, 2013, 3: 5)

Diplomacy in Islam

Prophet Muhammad never showed himself as the rigid and narrow-minded diplomat, but he always accepted negotiation and disliked armed combat as solution. For instance in the case of Charter of Medina, Prophet Muhammad attempted to negotiate with all these people of Medina and the Jews, and later the negotiation had been documented which is known as “Constitution of Medina”. It is a document of great historical significance. The provisions of the Treaty itself really showed the credibility of Prophet Muhammad as diplomat. Another remarkable diplomatic practice of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) can be clearly notice in the Treaty of Hudaibiyah. In this Treaty he really exhibited to Muslims the real art of negotiation. As a peace-oriented diplomat Prophet Muhammad preserved peace and offered negotiation even when his attention to enter Mecca was deterred by the Quraisyh. Prophet Muhammad (SAW) during the negotiation upheld the principle of tolerance, persuasion and patience. Prophets diplomacy really enabled him to handle this extremely complicated and fragile negotiation. Even the terms of the Treaty were unfavorable to the Muslims Prophet Muhammad still did not react aggressively. Indeed the Prophets political foresight and diplomacy later led to the clear victory of Islam in the following years. Initially, diplomatic procedures were

adopted in Islamic history as a means of spreading the word of Islam. The Prophet (PBUH) dispatched emissaries to the kings and princes ruling at the time, inviting them to embrace Islam, a practice that the Rightly-guided caliphs emulated following on the path of the Prophet. The advent of Islam in the Arabian Peninsula is considered as a major paradigm shift at all levels, especially at the political level as it is related to the external relations of the Islamic state. Although, the Arabic diplomacy in the pre-Islamic era was also associated with foreign relations more commercial interests, however, the diplomatic practices in Islam went beyond such boundaries of the pre-Islamic era, and flied to all directions. There are religious texts in the holy Qur'an and in the Sunnah of the Prophet (PBUH) that cares and encourages diplomatic immunities. The texts represent the greatest respect for the human dignities, and it provides him with everything that will preserve him the dignity, such as personal immunity, privileges, virtue and many examples that we shall see in dealing of the holy Prophet (PBUH), which He (PBUH) established and affirmed the fundamentals, and which was continued after him by the rightly guided Caliphs.

The origin of the principle of diplomatic immunity in Islam is the maxim which is actually word of the holy Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) that says (do no harm). Therefore immunity that was established by the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) is that an envoy should not be killed. Instead, envoy must be allowed to return safely, whether the other party accept or reject the message that he brought. Since the beginning of his prophethood to the end of his life, the Prophet met with many delegates. The envoys that came to meet the Prophet were called Wafd meaning the delegate body. Some of the historians have reported that the Prophet sent over 300 letters to the tribe chiefs, state leaders and religious authorities. Furthermore the Prophet's behavior consistent with Quranic teachings is highly appreciable as he receives the envoys and representatives of foreign states as his guests. The ambassadors were received and stayed in Dar-ul-Zeyfan (guesthouse) that was protected and safe, which is considered as an example of the impunity of diplomatic and consular accommodation. It was customary to give presents to the envoys. History records examples of the Prophet's presents to envoys. Freedom was given to

the envoys to perform their religious right. The seventh to ninth year of Hijrah (Post Hudaibiyah and Fall of Mecca) can be regarded as the “Age of Deputation”. Some of the deputation received by the Prophet Muhammad like Banu Ashja, Banu Juhaina, Banu Muzainah, Banu Saad bin Bakar, Banu Tamim and also some deputation from Southern Arabia like the envoys of Oman, Yemen and Bahrain. Even Prophet (PBUH) also gave a great welcome and a kind treatment to the deputation from Christian state like Christian Najran and Princess of Banu Kindah from Hadralmaut. Prophet Muhammad in managing the political affairs of the state devised his own tool of diplomacy which is largely practice in today’s political affairs such as negotiation, sending a diplomat abroad, signing a treaty and arbitration. As far as practice of diplomacy under rightly guided Caliphs is concerned just like in the time of Prophet Muhammad, the era of his foremost successors, also recorded some diplomatic relations with foreign States. This era witnessed tremendous exchange of envoys between the Muslims and non-Muslim states. Further regarding the origin of the diplomacy in Islam it originated in the time of the Prophet. The Prophet had sent his emissaries in different places such as Al-Abbas was sent to Makkah, Anas Ibn Abi Murthid al-Ghanawi to Awas (near Taif) and Munzir Ibn Amir-al-Said to Najad. Moreover regarding the permanent diplomacy in Islam is concerned, Dr Hamidullah was of the opinion that it was totally temporary in the beginning stage. The permanent diplomacy came into existence during the reign of banu Umayyad and lives into account till the destruction of Baghdad by Mongols in 656 A.H. Under the Umayyad Caliphs diplomatic intercourse with neighboring Kingdoms has attained the height of ‘sophistication’. The Muawiyah Ibn Abi Sufyan (602-680 AD), an Umayyad Caliph, was known for his preference for diplomatic methods which has been observed to be a reason behind the longevity of his reign. These periods also witnessed quite a number of Muslims sent on diplomatic missions to the courts of various potentates for reasons ranging from political, commercial to social purposes. And on some other occasions, just for the purpose of exchanging friendly gifts. Finally it demonstrates that Prophet Muhammad gave a moral basis to diplomacy and the art which was distrusted, because of its inglorious record, came to assume a mission and a meaning unfamiliar to its earlier

adepts. In addition some of the main objectives of diplomacy being a peaceful solution of international problems and promotion of harmony between different states, therefore it should be of interest to see how the Prophet Muhammad who was also head of a state, achieved these objectives by the well-known methods of diplomacy, i.e., negotiation, conciliation, mediation and arbitration.

Conclusion

Islam is one the fastest growing religion in the world. One among many reasons, it stands for peace, urges for peace and invites people towards peace. The Prophet Muhammad (pbuh) was sent to spread mercy to all mankind regardless of colour, creed, sex and nation. Islam believes in borderless society where everyone entitled to justice, equality and freedom which also emphasized in its relations with others. Qur'an says: "Allah does not forbid you to deal justly and kindly with those who fought not against you on account of religion and did not drive you out of your homes. Verily, Allah loves those who deal with equity" (60:8) In conclusion the Holy Prophet, with respect to existing traditions and Quran teachings, signed diplomatic negotiations in ties with Arabian tribes and other states. The Prophet implemented this method by delegating ambassadors or representatives to different countries. The Prophet never showed himself as the rigid and narrow-minded diplomat, but he always accepted negotiation and disliked armed combat as solution. Initially, diplomatic procedures were adopted in Islamic history as a means of spreading the word of Islam. There are religious texts in the holy Qur'an and in the Sunnah of the Prophet (PBUH) that cares and encourages diplomatic immunities. Moreover the era of rightly guided Caliphs witnessed tremendous exchange of envoys between the Muslims and non-Muslim states. Further regarding the permanent diplomacy in Islam is concerned it came into existence during the reign of banu Umayyad. Finally the Prophet (PBUH) gave a moral basis to diplomacy and the art which was distrusted, because of its inglorious record, came to assume a mission and a meaning unfamiliar to its earlier adepts.

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